

Sending Windows Firewall Logs to Graylog – A Practical Guide

Dominik Altermatt

Offense Department, scip AG
doal@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Abstract: Windows Firewall logging is disabled by default. The format of the Windows Firewall logs cannot simply be imported into Graylog. Graylog and NXLog offer all the necessary features for collecting Windows Firewall logs.

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180719> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

To monitor logs from the on-board firewall on your Windows clients/servers and analyze suspicious or unusual activity, the best approach is to send logs to a *central security log monitoring solution*. In our test lab we show you one way to do this, which involves sending Windows Firewall logs from a Windows 10 client to *Graylog* [1].

To set up a separate Graylog instance, you can refer to the instructions from the relevant manufacturer. For the test lab, we installed a current *CentOS* [2] on a VM and installed a current version of *Graylog* [3]. We chose *NXLog Community Edition* [4] as the log shipper on the Windows client.

3. Activate Windows Firewall logs

You may (or may not) be surprised that logging of the on-board firewall is not activated on Windows clients and servers by default. That means you have to activate in order to collect log data.

Windows Firewall logging can be activated by going to *Windows Defender Firewall with Advanced Security* -> *Properties* -> *[Domain/Private/Public] Profile tab* -> *Logging Customize*.

Then change the value *No (Default)* for the items *Log dropped packets* and *Log successful connections* to *Yes*. It is also a good idea to change the *size limit* of the log file to at least 16384 KB.

You can also achieve the same result with the following group policies:

Setting	Group Policy	Recommen
Log file size limit	Computer Configuration\Policies\Windows Settings\Security Settings\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall Properties\Domain Profile\Logging Customize\Size limit (KB)	16384 KB greater
Log dropped packets	Computer Configuration\Policies\Windows Settings\Security Settings\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall Properties\Domain Profile\Logging Customize\Log dropped packets	Yes
Log successful connections	Computer Configuration\Policies\Windows Settings\Security Settings\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall with Advanced Security\Windows Firewall Properties\Domain Profile\Logging Customize\Log successful connections	Yes

4. Configure NXLog

Once you have installed NXlog on the Windows system following the manufacturer's instructions, you will also need to configure it. Since the recipient will be a Graylog instance, the Firewall logs should be sent using the *Graylog Extended Log Format* [5] (GELF) via UDP.

The relevant settings are found in the NXLog configuration file located in its installation directory (default path):

```
C:\Program Files (x86)\nxlog\conf\nxlog.conf
```

The following changes are made in `nxlog.conf`. The default configuration file serves as the starting point.

4.1. 1. Activate GELF

1. The default log format is syslog, but you can comment out this line using the `#` symbol
2. The GELF module is added on a new line
3. The name of the extension is changed from `_syslog` to `_gelf`

```
<Extension _gelf>
  Module      xm_gelf
  #Module     xm_syslog
</Extension>
```

4.2. 2. Configure log input

1. The `im_vistalog` module was replaced by `im_file` to allow reading from a file log
2. Then the path of the log file is defined, in our case here: File
"C:\Windows\system32\LogFiles\Firewall\pfirewall.all.log"
3. An `exec` statement is also required here. This reads the timestamp of a log line using regex and writes it in the designated field in GELF so that Graylog can then write the correct timestamp of the log line in the dedicated field. Without this `exec` statement, Graylog would receive and display an incorrect timestamp, thus preventing the adequate analysis of the log files. There may be other, more efficient ways to do this, but for the purposes of the test lab we thought this solution was acceptable.
4. The name of the `<input>` is changed to `WinFirewallLog`

```
<Input WinFirewallLog>
  Module      im_file
  File
  "C:\Windows\system32\LogFiles\Firewall\pfirewall.all.log"
  Exec        if $raw_event =~ /(\d\d\d\d\d\d-\d\d-\d\d \d\d:\d\d:\d\d)/ {$EventTime =
  strftime($1, '%Y-%m-%d%t%H:%M:%S');}
  # For windows 2003 and earlier use the
  following:
  # Module     im_mseventlog
</Input>
```

4.3. 3. Configure Graylog as recipient

1. The `om_tcp` module was replaced by `om_udp`
2. The IP address of the Graylog server is entered as `host`
3. An available listener port of the Graylog server is entered as the `port`
4. The existing `exec` statement is commented out with `#` characters to disable it
5. The `Exec $ShortMessage = $raw_event;` statement is added. This ensures that the entire log line is sent in the `Message` field. Without this statement, the message would be truncated to 64 characters.
6. The `OutputType` is defined as `GELF` in a separate line
7. The name of the output is left as the default value `out`

```
<Output out>
  Module      om_udp
  Host        192.168.1.10
  Port        12202
  Exec        $ShortMessage = $raw_event;
  #Exec       to_syslog_snare();
  OutputType  GELF
</Output>
```

4.4. 4. Restart NXLog Service to apply the new configuration

If you are already sending *Windows event logs via NXLog* [6] or would like to do so, make sure to define a separate `<input>`, `<output>` and `<route>` for each log item in the NXLog configuration. This could look as follows:

1. Each `<input>` is defined with a corresponding name – here they are `<Input WinEventLog>` and `<Input WinFirewallLog>`
2. Two separate `<Output>`, each defined with a different port. This means that in Graylog you can define a specific input for each port for the different log items and analyze them separately. Here they are `<Output out1>` and `<Output out2>`.
3. Now you need two `<Route>` definitions with the format `Input => Output`. So one `<Route>` is defined with `Path WinEventLog => out1` and one with `Path WinFirewallLog => out2`.

```
<Input WinEventLog>
  Module      im_msvistalog
</Input>

<Input WinFirewallLog>
  Module      im_file
  File
  "C:\Windows\system32\LogFiles\Firewall\pfirewall.all.log"
  Exec        if $raw_event =~ /(\d\d\d\d\d\d-\d\d-\d\d \d\d:\d\d:\d\d)/ {$EventTime =
  strftime($1, '%Y-%m-%d%t%H:%M:%S');}
</Input>

<Output out1>
  Module      om_udp
  Host        192.168.1.10
  Port        12201
  OutputType  GELF
</Output>

<Output out2>
  Module      om_udp
  Host        192.168.1.10
  Port        12202
  Exec        $ShortMessage = $raw_event;
  OutputType  GELF
</Output>

<Route 1>
  Path        WinEventLog => out1
</Route>

<Route 2>
  Path        WinFirewallLog => out2
</Route>
```

5. Configure Graylog

So that Graylog can now receive the logs, you need to define a corresponding input:

1. Log in to the Graylog web console
2. Open *System -> Input* in the top menu
3. On the input page, select UDP GELF in the dropdown and click on *Launch new input*
4. Enter the required data in the relevant window:
 1. Select current Graylog node
 2. Give the input a name, such as `WindowsClient_FirewallLogs`
 3. Enter the bind address of the Graylog server: `192.168.1.10` (from the `<output>` in `nxlog.conf`)
 4. Enter the corresponding port `12202` (from the `<output>` in `nxlog.conf`)
 5. For the test lab, we kept the default values for all other settings

Now Graylog is ready to receive the first logs. Because the test lab is using a CentOS for Graylog, it is also important to ensure that a corresponding port has been opened on the CentOS firewall.

Currently, the individual fields of the log line are displayed as a string in the Message field. However, this prevents Graylog from being used to analyze all fields. Graylog also comes with an extractor which can read the incoming logs, using *GROK* [7] for instance, and write them to the corresponding fields in Graylog.

Graylog already offers a selection of *GROK patterns*. These need to be modified somewhat for the log lines of the Windows Firewall log, so that `-` is sent as a placeholder for unpopulated values. This means that the minus sign is added to the GROK pattern that is used for the firewall log extractor.

In the Graylog web console, you can manage GROK patterns under *System->GROK Patterns*. To map all fields of the Windows Firewall log line with a GROK pattern, the following new GROK patterns were created on the basis of existing patterns.

Original GROK pattern	With minus sign	Name of the GROK pattern
INT	<code>%{INT} [-]</code>	WINFIREWALL_INT
WORD	<code>%{WORD} [-]</code>	WINFIREWALL_WORD
IP	<code>(?:%{IPV6} %{IPV4}) [-]</code>	WINFIREWALL_IP

Now you should be able to create the extractor:

1. Under the previously created input, go to *Manage Extractor -> Add Extractor -> Get Started*

2. A submenu will appear with the button *Load Message*; here you can search incoming log messages, or call up a specific message by entering its ID. This allows you to test the extractor in the next steps.
3. After clicking the button, the message will appear, and you can configure an extractor for each field. In our case this needs to be done for the *Message* field using *GROK Pattern*.
4. The following GROK pattern can now be entered into the designated field: `%{DATESTAMP:UNWANTED} %{WINFIREWALL_WORD:action} %{WINFIREWALL_WORD:protocol} %{WINFIREWALL_IP:src-ip} %{WINFIREWALL_IP:dst-ip} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:src-port} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:dst-port} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:size} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:tcpflags} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:tcpsyn} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:tcpack} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:tcpwin} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:icmpptype} %{WINFIREWALL_INT:icmpcode} %{WINFIREWALL_WORD:info} %{WINFIREWALL_WORD:path}`
5. The *Try* button lets you test whether the pattern works straight away
6. Finally, add the extractor
7. Now you can use Graylog functions to analyze all fields from the Windows Firewall log lines

To avoid a possible off-set in the Graylog Message Timestamps, the Graylog time zone needs to be changed accordingly. In our case to CET. The change needs to happen in a configuration file of Graylog, which can be found under `/etc/graylog/server/server.conf`.

```
root_timezone = CET
```

After a restart of the Graylog service one can use all features of Graylog to analyse the fields of Windows Firewall log-lines.

6. Conclusion

In the context of a lab set-up you can quickly and easily create and operate central security log monitoring through the firewall logs of your own Windows population – as soon as you have worked out how to process logs in a useful format in Graylog. There may well be simpler or more efficient methods for the format problems present in Windows Firewall logs, but for an initial test this approach is certainly adequate. If you are planning something similar in a production environment, don't forget *hardening* [8] for both Graylog itself and its host.

You can find more information on security logging in *our* [9] *articles* [10].

7. External Links

[1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170302>

[2] <https://centos.org/download/>

[3] <https://www.graylog.org>

[4] <https://nxlog.co/products/nxlog-community-edition>

[5] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180315>

[6] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20141106>

[7] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130405>

[8] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130905>

[9] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20121122>

[10] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20121127>